

A REVIEW ON “ROLE OF ROBOTICS IN PHARMACY”**Shubham Kumar Sajan^{1*}, Prabhu Dayal Rajan², Anchal Rai³**¹Assistant Professor, IEC Group of Institutes, Greater Noida U.P, India.²Assistant Professor, Mangalmay Pharmacy College, Greater Noida U.P India.³Assistant Professor, IEC Group of Institutes, Greater Noida U.P, India.

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ABSTRACT

Robots are proving advantageous in filling, inspection, packaging, laboratories, and the manufacture of personalized medicine. Automation, including automated inspection and packaging, is becoming an increasingly important part of pharmaceutical manufacturing. The many benefits of automation include efficiency, saving workers from hazardous environments or repetitive tasks, reducing training overhead, eliminating human error, increasing repeatability and reproducibility, and in cleanrooms, removing the potential for human contamination. Pharmaceutical companies are increasingly partnering with automation and robotics solutions providers to integrate these technologies into processes such as drug development, manufacturing, and anti-counterfeiting. Automation technologies can boost the speed of the

manufacturing process and make it safer and efficient, while also reducing manpower cost.

Clemson University and Nephron Pharmaceuticals Corporation, for example, have developed a benchtop robot that can fill, cap and seal sterile pre-filled syringes, which can reduce costs by preventing drug overfill and minimizing contamination. Filling syringes in the absence of a robot is a highly regulated process that needs to be undertaken by specialized technicians under ISO-certified clean rooms. The robot is expected to help in addressing the shortage of pre-filled syringes in hospitals and healthcare facilities. Robotic technology is being used for vial-filling applications on slower speed applications.

KEYWORDS: Robotics, Automation, Accuracy, Pharmaceutical field.

INTRODUCTION

A robot is a mechanical artificial agent and practically it is an electromechanical system. The Robotics Institute of America defines a robot as a Reprogrammable multifunctional manipulator designed to move materials, parts, tools, or specialized devices through variable programmed motions for the performance of a variety of tasks.^[1]

These robots are as fast as humans [at some times faster by 4 times] and are capable of working in shifts. In the Pharmaceutical industry, they have to follow strict rules and regulations and standards. If they commit anything wrong, then the whole event will be affected. For this purpose, the manufactures slowly started to automate their industry. One such move is bringing robots into their industry for helping them and reduces human time. Today lots of pharma manufactures are using robots for manufacturing certain drugs. There are also few benefits with the involvement of automation in Pharma company such as.

- (i) reduced amount of wastage,
- (ii) better safety, and
- (iii) less cost.

Isaac Aminov's: Three laws of robotics

Isaac Aminov was a science-fiction author who wrote the 'Three Laws of Robotics,' with the fourth law, known as the 'Zeroth Law,' added later. They are as follows

A robot must not injure a human being.

Except where such directives clash with the First Law, a robot shall obey directions provided to it by humans.

If it does not clash with the First or Second Laws, a robot must defend its own existence.

A robot must not harm humanity.

Types of robots

In pharmaceutical manufacturing, there are three categories of industrial robots

Cartesian

(Cartesian robot showing x, y and z axes)

Cartesian robots include two linear slides which are placed at 90-degree angles to each other which are then accompanied with a motorized unit that moves horizontally along the slides in the z axis, which moves up and down in the vertical plane. The quill holds the robots end-effector, such as gripper. A fourth axis (t/θ), it allows the quill to rotate in the horizontal plane. The main advantage of Cartesian robots is that they are less expensive, although their restricted range of motion has a limiting effect on their range. They're frequently used in automated systems or devices that specialize in a certain task, such as assay testing.^[2,3]

Selective Compliance Articulated Robot Arm (SCARA) robots

SCARA stands for selective compliance articulated robot arm. This refers to the arm segments, or links, of a SCARA being able to freely move but only in one geometrical plane. Most SCARAs has four axes, but three axis and five axis SCARA robots are also found. A SCARA has first two links that swivel left and right in the horizontal plane around the first two axes. In SCARA robot quill is the third link, which moves up and down along the third axis in the vertical plane. The quill rotates horizontally in the fourth axis but is unable to tilt at a vertical angle.^[4]

Articulated robots

(Articulated robots)

ROBOTICS ADVANCES AND INVESTMENTS

Swisslog just recently introduced the TransCar Automated Guided Vehicle—an automated system for moving heavy payloads from loading docks to their final destinations, smoothly integrating with elevators and doors to navigate. Laser, sonic and photographic guidance systems all work in tandem to help the AGV operate efficiently. Obviously, that makes the AGV a hugely attractive proposition just about anywhere where massive payloads are delivered and have to be sorted out regularly. So we're talking about hospitals, schools, universities, cafeterias, hotels, perhaps even airports and train stations.

Amazon (NASDAQ: AMZN) recently acquired Kiva Systems for \$775 million or so; Kiva manufactures robotic systems for moving large payloads around in warehouses. Clearly, robotics is revealing itself as an area that attracts diverse minds for diverse purposes. Healthcare, hospitals, and pharmacies will see booming business in the near future as the baby boomer generation hits retirement. Expect to see major advances in healthcare-related robotics soon.^[5]

Technical Principle of Raman Hyperspectrum

The Raman hyperspectral analysis method was originally discovered by the Indian scientist Chandrasekhara Venkata Raman to destroy optical molecules. The analysis method uses the spectra of different incident light frequencies to analyze. The Raman Effect refers to the elastic and inelastic scattering of light when it irradiates a substance. Inelastic scattering has

components that are longer and shorter than the excitation wavelength. Among them, the spectral lines of the in elastically scattered light that are different from the incident light frequency are called Raman lines, the Raman lines whose frequency is less than the incident light frequency are called Stokes lines, and those with greater frequency are called anti-Stokes lines.

Raman Hyperspectral Hardware System

Raman hyper spectrometer is also called grating dispersion Raman hyper spectrometer, which is mainly composed of excitation light source, external optical path, optical dispersion system and calculation processing system.

Raman hyperspectral system structure figure. This system mainly consists of laser, spectrograph, CCD device and other optical devices.

Application of Hyperspectral Imaging Technology in Detection

Compared with the situation where Raman hyperspectral detection relies on spectral curves for data analysis, hyper-spectral imaging technology has realized the leap from one-dimensional line spectroscopy to two-dimensional imaging plane. Not only has the amount of hyperspectral data greatly enriched but also it contains spatial plane information that cannot be obtained by Raman hyper spectroscopy. In this way, it could expand the application scenarios of hyper-spectroscopy and contribute to the extended application of hyperspectral technology in pharmaceutical inspection and other agricultural and forestry, as well as forensic criminal investigation fields. Applications and methods of hyperspectral imaging in pharmaceutical detection.

Detection of Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients

In the detection of active pharmaceutical ingredients, the detection of Raman hyperspectroscopy is limited to the sampling of surface points, and it is impossible to comprehensively and accurately detect and analyze the distribution, uniformity, and other indicators of active pharmaceutical ingredients. Hyperspectral imaging technology overcomes the limitations of Raman hyperspectral point sampling and detecting, and performs wide-band imaging of drugs within a certain field of view, and obtains spectral images of drugs at various wavelengths.

Detecting the coating thickness of tablets with Raman spectroscopy method. The left figure indicates the optical image of cross-section of the tablet after cleaving and the right diagram indicates the prediction result the drug samples.

Detecting the coating thickness of tablets with Raman spectroscopy method. The left figure indicates the optical image of cross-section of the tablet after cleaving and the right diagram indicates the prediction result the drug sample.

Robots for filling, inspection, and packaging

Robotic technology is being used for vial-filling applications on slower speed applications. "Robotic vial manipulation transfers components from station to station both before and after filling and pack-off," says Walt Langosch, director of sales and marketing at ESS Technologies. The company also has experience with handling plastic and glass prefilled syringes in pre- process, buffering, and initial and end-of-line packaging.

(Robots for filling, inspection, and packaging)

Robots for producing personalized medicines

Custom automation and contract-manufacturing company Invetech recently partnered with biopharmaceutical company Argos Therapeutics to develop automated manufacturing systems based on Argos' Arcelis technology platform for personalized immunotherapies. "The Arcelis platform uses two, five-axis robotic arms in the production of the mRNA from a patient's tumor, which is used as the antigen for loading into the dendritic cells produced in the cellular processing equipment," explains Richard Grant, director of cell therapy at Invetech. "The cellular equipment uses automation to manipulate the white blood cells throughout the manufacturing process to control their development and maturation into dendritic cells. These cells express the desired antigens, which when delivered to a patient, will trigger the patient's immune system to produce killer T-cells that will target the metastatic tumors".^[8]

Detection of Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients and Coating Thickness of Tablets

The detection of active pharmaceutical ingredients in pharmaceuticals products generally refers to the quantitative determination of active ingredients in drugs. . As for the quantitative measurement of acetylsalicylic acid in drugs, Szostak et al., detected the Raman hyperspectral images of powder and tablets using the peak intensity, PCR and PLS methods which achieves excellent performance. In addition, Frosch et al.^[9,10]

Detection of Herbal Medicines

Herbal medicine has received extensive attention from pharmaceutical workers and patients in recent years. Its mild therapeutic effects and unique pharmacological effects have excellent effects in the treatment of many diseases. However, the quality control of herbal medicines has always been a difficult problem. On the one hand, the quality identification of medicinal

materials usually relies on manual experience, which is easily interfered by human subjective factors, on the other hand, it is difficult to accurately detect the quality of medicinal materials by machine vision. Hyperspectral imaging technology has natural advantages in herbal medicine detection. Wide- band imaging could accurately detect and analyze herbal medicines of various varieties, origins, and seasons, which brings great convenience to the quality detection of herbal medicines.^[11]

Sorting Detection of Different Types of Tablets

Tablets of the same color but different types often appear in the drug sorting process of pharmaceutical companies. At this time, industrial cameras are not able to distinguish the tablets, and hyperspectral imaging technology is helpful to classify and sort the tablets with the characteristics of different light reflectance on the surface of different drug components.^[12]

Nano robots

Nano robots are referred to as tiny robots or tiny machines which can traverse through the human body very easily. When a nano robot enters into the body of a patient, it would seek for infected cells and would repair them without causing any damage to the healthy cells. The nano manipulators of nano robots will penetrate into the damaged or targeted cell while the nano robots remain outside to avoid any possibility if present of causing damage to the intracellular skeleton. These nano robots provide an advantage such as extreme life prolongation through cell surgery after the entry of nano robots in human blood stream. Coordination is required across the board for better communication, acting, and sensing and poses a major research challenge.^[13]

Benefits of using pharmaceutical robots Design Advantage

In the pharmaceutical business, slim, rapid, and flexible robots are suitable for pick-and-place and assembly tasks. Industrial robots can construct blood sugar kits and other custom orders thanks to vision technology.

Advantage of Safety

Robots safeguard the integrity of pharmaceutical products as well as the health of employees and patients. Toxic chemicals can be safely mixed using industrial robots. These specific robot models are intended for use in clean room environments. These models never contaminate product due to their sealed arm construction and decontamination with

Hydrogen Peroxide Vapor (HPV). Low payloads pick and place jobs that would be too difficult for human workers are now in the hands of tenacious robots.

Reliability

All medication must be tracked and traced throughout the manufacturing process, according to the Food and Drug Administration (FDA). Pharmaceutical companies can meet these requirements more easily thanks to industrial robots. Robots, in a similar vein, reduce accidents and waste. Another reason for relying on robots is that they can work nonstop for 24 hours a day, seven days a week.

Tirelessness

A robot can complete a 96-hour project in ten hours with greater consistency and higher quality results.

Return on investment (ROI)

ROI has a quick turnaround. Furthermore, as quality and application speed improve, the benefits of increased production possibilities become available.

Accuracy

Robotic systems outperform humans in terms of accuracy and consistency.

Affordability

More pick and place robotic cells are being implemented for automation applications as technology progresses and more affordable robotics become available.

Quality

Robots have the potential to significantly improve product quality. Every application is executed with precision and high Repeatability. This level of consistency is difficult to achieve in any other way.

Production

Throughput speeds increase with robots, which has a direct impact on production. Robots have the potential to produce more than human workers because they can work at a constant speed without stopping for breaks, sleep, or vacations.^[14,15]

CONCLUSION

Robotics which has emerged as a newer and advanced field in pharmacy has gained much non popularity in pharma industry. Their applicability in different fields of pharma industry is appreciated. It is accepted that in future the robotics would play a vital role for the development and growth of pharmaceutical sciences. The pharmaceutical industry is looking for automation due to high competition and to provide drugs to customers at a low-cost Robotics will play a significant role in the field of Pharmacy. It is expected that the number of industrial robots installed would increase by 25% in 2023 and 2024 as well The pharmaceutical industry, in turn, is favorable to robotic systems because its processes generally require low forces, take place in clean environments, and include predictable sets of operations. Pharmaceutical industries are intently seeking ways to reduce their expenses, increase their efficiency, and make high-quality products. Robots can help companies achieve these ends by providing speed, precision, repeatability, and flexibility. The future is always hard to predict, but it will be determined by technological developments, commercial factors and by changes within the pharmaceutical industry.

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